

The use of microbial inoculants in winter cereals

Improving crop resistance to diseases and pests by enhancing soil and plant health

Microorganisms form important symbioses in the soil. They are indispensable in any cultivation system. To make a crop more resistant to diseases and pests, inoculants containing microorganisms can be applied. There is already a great deal of knowledge about microbial inoculants, but the scientific basis for them is lacking. This exploratory trial was a first step in Flanders (Belgium) to focus attention on the application of microbial inoculants.

Introduction

Plant inoculation is a practice that has been around for over 100 years (European Union, 2023). Bacteria and fungi can form a symbiotic relationship with plants, which can result in:

- Plants becoming more efficient at taking up nutrients from the soil or through their leaves.
- Plants becoming more resistant to biotic stress caused by diseases or pests.
- Higher yields.

Microorganisms interact with plants in various ways.

Direct interactions occur in the soil or with pathogens, leading to benefits such as increased nutrient availability for the plant and the production of antimicrobial substances. **Indirect interactions** occur through the plant itself: microorganisms can trigger the release of signal molecules that strengthen the plant's immune system (like "vaccinating" the plant) or stimulate the production of hormones that promote plant growth.

In some agricultural systems, symbiosis may not be entirely successful because beneficial microbial strains are absent or nutrient availability is insufficient to stimulate them. By adding microbial strains in the form of preparations or (liquid) fermentation products, we can promote symbiosis between plants and microorganisms in any agricultural system.

The best-known inoculants are Rhizobium bacteria (*Bradyrhizobium spp.*), which form symbiotic rela-

tionships with legumes and are important for nitrogen fixation in root nodules. Mycorrhizae (*Glomus spp.*) improve the uptake of phosphorus and other minerals. Other known microorganisms are Trichoderma, Pseudomonas and Bacillus as biocontrol organisms and/or plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria.

In this trial, we worked with a commercial product (Soil Activator, <https://earthalivect.com/soil-activator/>) containing Pseudomonas and Bacillus. It is a USDA Certified Bio-Based Product which is reported to improve crop yield and quality. In addition, we tested two self-prepared products (Jadam Microbial Solution and EM Cubana) containing microorganisms derived from forest litter. These two products support plant growth by boosting soil biology, strengthening plant resilience and improving nutrient cycling. Although you can use them on your farm, they are not certified, which can be a problem for organic production. It is important to check it with your local control authority. Finally, we also include a silica-based product manufactured by Jean Premiski (referred to here as Silica). It also has the property of making plants more stress resilient. Silica has been included for comparison purposes, but it is not a biostimulant.

Challenges

The use of microbial inoculants is still relatively unknown in Flanders (Belgium). Within regenerative agriculture, however, farmers are increasingly seeking alternatives to make their crops more resilient. JADAM Microbial Solution (Youngsang, 2016) is well-known in Korean Natural and Organic Farming, while EM Cubana (Dorian, 2015) originates from South America. In Flanders, a few pioneering farmers are already working with these products and bringing others together to test them during workshops. Although the group of participants is small, they are already convinced of the products' effectiveness. On the other hand, the lack of scientific trial data makes other farmers more cautious. A commercial product like Soil Activator is expected to have been tested for the viability of its microorganisms and overall effectiveness. This is harder to verify for a homemade mixture. You can use your sense of smell; it should not have an unpleasant odour, and pH can also serve as a useful indicator. To be completely certain, a sample can be sent to a certified laboratory for testing.

Disadvantages

Farmers are increasingly interested in using microbial inoculants, but widespread adoption remains limited.

One key reason is the lack of sufficient scientific trials and research. Within the OH-FINE project, we are working to establish a more scientific foundation and to translate our findings into practical guidance for farmers.

The effectiveness of inoculants depends heavily on environmental factors such as drought, sunlight intensity at the time of application, and soil conditions. Even technical aspects, such as spray pressure during crop treatment, can affect whether the microorganisms survive. At present, there is still too little knowledge about the optimal timing and application methods.

In addition, the brewing process used to prepare inoculants is relatively new to many farmers (Dorian, 2015; Youngsang, 2016). Mistakes in this process can reduce the viability of the microorganisms. Since inoculants involve living organisms, proper storage conditions are also essential, but currently not well understood. Moreover, microbial inoculants generally have a limited shelf life and need to be applied shortly after preparation to maintain their effectiveness.

There are, of course, commercial products available that simplify the process for farmers. However, these products remain sensitive to environmental influences, which continue to pose challenges for consistent effectiveness. Commercial products also cost considerably more than self-made products. For example, Soil Activator costs 320 euros per hectare, while Jadam Microbial Solutions costs 87 euros per hectare.

Key benefits

The use of microorganism-based inoculants offers benefits for farmers, as they can enhance and reinforce natural processes. These inoculants can improve interactions between plants and soil life, leading to stronger, more resilient crops (Dorian, 2015; Youngsang, 2016). However, it often takes time for farmers to become fully convinced of their effectiveness. Biostimulants tend to be most effective when soil conditions are suboptimal, as they can help restore soil health and support plant growth under stress or nutrient-limited circumstances.

At the same time, fewer chemical plant protection products and fertilisers are being approved, and some have already been removed from the market. As a result, farmers are being encouraged to seek alternative solutions. Microbial inoculants are being used in a variety of ways.

One well-known example in Flanders (Belgium) is the application of Rhizobium bacteria in soybean cultivation. We are also observing growing interest among organic and regenerative farmers, many of whom have already begun experimenting with these products or plan to do so soon.

According to De Long *et al.* (2021), the benefits of biostimulants include:

- improved overall plant growth and germination,
- increased yield,
- enhanced nutrient uptake and metabolic efficiency,
- binding of heavy metals and other toxic substances through chelation,
- improved soil structure and functioning,
- higher total nutrient content in harvested products,
- better quality, shelf life, and resistance to both abiotic and biotic stress.

Field trial

1. Objectives and research question

Microbial inoculants are agents that can stimulate natural processes in plants, thereby improving nutrient uptake and crop resistance. We are investigating the impact of certain microbial inoculants on crop yield and disease susceptibility in winter wheat.

2. Applying microbial inoculants using drones

When farmers want to treat their crops during the season, time is often limited. As the crop grows, using agricultural machinery can cause more damage. The use of microbial inoculants is only interesting when it can be applied until flowering.

In this trial, we used a drone for application (Figure 1). However, regulations in Flanders are strict, and spraying drones cannot be used everywhere. A suitable location

was found for the trial, but in practice, this will not always be easy for farmers. In addition, spraying drones are still expensive, and operators must hold a pilot's license.

Advantages of using a spraying drone:

- Enables treatment in hard-to-reach areas
- Allows application later in the season
- Supports site-specific application
- Reduces soil compaction

Disadvantages of using a drone

- Limited control over treatment at higher heights
- Challenges in achieving uniform spray distribution
- Restricted capacity due to tank size and battery life
- Subject to complex regulations in Flanders

3. Experimental set-up

This trial was conducted at the Experimental Platform for Agroecology in Hansbeke (Belgium) in a population of winter wheat, var. *Mariagertoba* (Figure 2). The plot was maintained by ILVO, and the harvest was delivered to an organic farmer. The field was cultivated organically; 2025 was the first year of the conversion to organic farming. It was a demonstration trial with four replicates set up in a non-randomised block design, as the applicability of drone spraying needed to be taken into account. An open field day was held at the Experimental Platform on 19 June 2025, showcasing the field trial and drone spraying operations (Figure 3). Three microbial-based products were tested, with rainwater serving as a control. The product selection was made in consulta-

Figure 1: Spraying drone in action during the second treatment of the winter wheat (photo taken on 25 April 2025).

Figure 2: Growing of winter wheat, photo taken on 6 May 2025.

tion with the platform's farmers and pioneers. Information on how to prepare the mixtures was obtained from these pioneers. The fifth product, Silica, was included because it shares similar characteristics with microbial inoculants, such as enhancing stress resistance, stimulating growth, and promoting yield. Table 1 contains information about the test objects.

Table 1: Composition, properties and expected results of the various test objects

	Soil Activator	JADAM Microbial Solution	EM Cubana	Silica
Origin	Commercial product	Self-made product	Self-made product	Commercial product
Composition	-	0,2 ha: Forest litter (20 g) + salt (20 g) + boiled potato (40 g) + rainwater (20 L)	0,2 ha: Solid EM (200 g) + molasses (20 g) + raw milk (200 ml) + rainwater (4L)	-
Preparation for 0.2 ha (spraying volume = 4L)	0.2 kg + 4 L rainwater	5 L of composition + 20 L rainwater	1 L of composition + 9 L rainwater	2,5 g + 8 L rainwater
Present micro-organisms	Bacillus & Pseudomonas	Originating from forest litter	Originating from forest litter + Lactobacillus	-
Expected results	Better crop yield and quality, better water retention	Boost soil biology, improved plant resilience	Boost soil biology, improved nutrient cycling	Improved plant tolerance to drought, improved resistance against diseases and pests, cell wall strengthening

Table 2: Technical information about the trial in Hansbeke (Belgium).

Parameter	Description
Type of trial	Demo trial, 5 treatments with four replicates.
Location	Hansbeke (N 51.081234, E 3.516711)
Crop	Winter cereal (wheat) – population wheat Mariagertoba
Trial Treatments	Soil Activator, Silica, JADAM Microbial Solution, EM Cubana, Rainwater (control)
Date of application	Tillering: 27 March 2025, Stem elongation: 25 April 2025, Before ear formation: 19 May 2025
Preceding crop	Maize
Fertilisation	No fertiliser used. An additional Stimulus treatment, a mixture of trace elements in solution with humic acids, was applied together with the second and third applications.
Monitoring	Plant height, chlorophyll content, number of ears, grain yield, protein content, hectoliter weight, thousand kernel weight (TKW)

During the growing season, treatments were applied using a drone, and a researcher monitored disease susceptibility, plant height, number of ears, and chlorophyll content. At harvest, a 38 m² plot was harvested for all 4 replicates of each treatment to determine yield. Protein content, thousand kernel weight, and hectolitre weight were then measured from a sample of approximately 1 kg.

Figure 3: Open field day at Experimental Platform for Agroecology in Hansbeke on 19 June 2025. Explanations were provided about the trial and the spraying drone. There was a great deal of interest.

Table 2 and Table 3 provide technical information about the trial and drone applications.

Table 4 provides an overview of the soil conditions at the start of the trial. It is a moderately acidic soil with a low organic matter content and moderate fertility. No fertiliser was applied during the trial. Stimulus (<https://www.gaiago.eu/produits/stimulus>) was applied only in the last two treatments. Stimulus is a plant prebiotic, a mixture of the trace elements manganese (Mn) and zinc (Zn) in a solution containing humic acids, applied at a rate of 3 L/ha.

Table 3: Technical information for drone applications (DJI, <https://www.dji.com/t10/specs>)

Working width	1,5 m
Spraying volume	4 L
Nozzle type	Teejet A I11002VS
Spray flow	1,7 m/s
Operation height (above crop)	1,5 m

Table 4: Soil characteristics at the start of the trial.

OC: organic carbon; pH-KCl: potential pH; C/N: ratio of organic carbon over total soil nitrogen; plant available nutrients (K, Mg, Ca & P) using Amlact method; HWC & HWP: hot water extractable carbon and phosphorus; CEC: cation exchange capacity; DM: dry matter.

Texture	Depth	OC	pH-KCl	C/N	K	Mg	Ca	P	HWC	HWP	CEC
	(cm)	(%)	-	-	(mg/100g DM)				(mg/kg DM)		(cmolc/kg DM)
Sandy loam	0-30	1,94	5,1	12,9	9,0	13,3	86	29,1	610,8	14,5	8,4
	30-60	0,91	4,9	14,9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

4. Results

The results were processed in RStudio, tested for an interaction in a two-way ANOVA, followed by a Tukey test at a 0.1 significance level.

Figure 4 shows the average number of ears per treatment. The number of ears was counted at three random locations per plot using a 1-m stick on 12 June 2025. There was heterogeneity not only between the plots of the same object but also within the plot itself, making it difficult to attribute differences in tillering to the treatments applied. It is noteworthy, however, that the plots treated with rainwater showed a lower number of ears. Based on the ear counts, the plots treated with Silica showed the highest number of ears.

Other measured parameters often also indicate that the rainwater-treated plots performed less well, but we cannot say with complete certainty that this is due to the treatments.

Figure 4: Number of ears (mean ± standard error) for the different microbial inoculant treatments EM Cubana, Soil Activator and JMS, as well as Silica and rainwater in winter wheat var. *Mariagertoba* (Hansbeke, Belgium). Different letters indicate statistically significant differences among treatments (significance level = 0.1).

Figure 5: Chlorophyll content (mean ± standard error) for the different microbial inoculant treatments EM Cubana, Soil Activator and JMS, as well as Silica and rainwater in winter wheat var. *Mariagertoba* (Hansbeke, Belgium). All treatments share the same letter, indicating no statistically significant differences (significance level = 0.1).

The chlorophyll content was measured on the flag leaf of 10 plants at a single point in time, 22 May 2025 (Figure 5). Plant height was measured on 20 plants per plot, randomly selected on 12 June 2025 (Figure 6). No significant differences were found for either parameter; however, there was a noticeable trend toward higher chlorophyll content in objects treated with Silica or JMS.

The harvest took place on 18 July 2025, when the wheat was ripe. The yield is presented at a moisture content of 15% (Figure 7). At harvest, the moisture content was slightly lower, averaging 14.4% (results not shown). The yield was lower than one would expect for wheat. The plot was not fertilised and only received two stimulus applications during the season. There are visible fluctuations, but these differences are not significant. The self-prepared products EM Cubana and JMS, together with the object Silica, gave a higher yield.

Figure 6: Plant height (cm) (mean ± standard error) for the different microbial inoculant treatments EM Cubana, Soil Activator and JMS, as well as Silica and rainwater in winter wheat var. *Mariagertoba* (Hansbeke, Belgium). All treatments share the same letter, indicating no statistically significant differences (significance level = 0.1).

Figure 7: Yield (15% moisture content) (kg/ha) grain (mean ± standard error) for the different microbial inoculant treatments EM Cubana, Soil Activator and JMS as well as Silica and rainwater in winter wheat var. *Mariagertoba* (Hansbeke, Belgium). All treatments share the same letter, indicating no statistically significant differences (significance level = 0.1).

The hectolitre weight (kg/hl) showed no significant differences and was similar for all objects, 80 kg/hl (results not shown). This value is normal for baking wheat. No significant differences were observed in protein content either (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Protein content (%) grain (mean \pm standard error) for the different microbial inoculant treatments EM Cubana, Soil Activator and JMS as well as Silica and rainwater in winter wheat var. *Mariagerstoba* (Hansbeke, Belgium). All treatments share the same letter, indicating no statistically significant differences (significance level = 0.1).

5. Conclusion

Few statistical differences were observed between the various products applied, even though differences, especially between the control and the other treatments, were expected.

Several factors may explain this outcome. Firstly, the plot itself may not have been fully suitable. A drone image clearly showed a large variation in crop performance, despite careful screening of satellite images from previous years when positioning the field trial. Secondly, the trial design was not sufficiently adapted to drone applications. A third possible explanation is that the test was conducted on a population wheat variety, which naturally contains more variation than a standard commercial variety. Furthermore, the microbial activity of both the commercial and self-prepared products was not evaluated.

In 2027, a new trial with microbial inoculants will be established, taking these lessons into account. It will be conducted at three locations across Flanders to include a range of soil types. If drones are used again for the application, the trial design will be further optimised. The major advantage of using drones is that they allow treatments to be applied later in the growing season.

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Further information

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